

CFRP RECYCLING METHOD COMPATIBLE WITH A WIDE RANGE OF EPOXY MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

We have developed a chemical recycling method for carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) using nitric acid decomposition. While carbon fiber (CF) recycling has been widely studied, reports focusing on the chemical recycling of the resin matrix in CFRP remain limited. In this study, we targeted the resin fraction of epoxy-based prepreg CFRP and successfully decomposed it under mild conditions (3 hours at 80 °C) using nitric acid. This process enabled the efficient separation and recovery of carbon fiber with minimal damage, while also allowing for the isolation of decomposed resin fragments.

Characterization of the resin decomposition products revealed the formation of nitro-containing aromatic compounds. Subsequent catalytic hydrogenation of these nitroaromatics yielded amine-functionalized compounds, which were evaluated as potential curing agents for new epoxy resins. The resulting recycled amines demonstrated reactivity comparable to conventional amine hardeners, indicating their applicability as a value-added recycled product. This approach not only contributes to the full recycling of CFRP components but also provides a pathway to upcycle the resin fraction into functional intermediates for polymer synthesis.

Our work highlights a viable strategy for the holistic recycling of thermoset-based CFRPs, addressing the sustainability challenges associated with composite materials. Further research is underway to optimize the reaction parameters, improve product yields, and evaluate the performance of resins cured with the recycled amines in real applications. This study represents a significant step toward establishing a closed-loop material cycle for CFRPs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) are composite materials that combine high-strength carbon fiber with a thermosetting polymer matrix, typically based on epoxy resins. Owing to their superior mechanical properties, low weight, and excellent corrosion resistance, CFRPs are widely adopted in high-performance applications such as aerospace structures, automotive parts, wind turbine blades, and sporting goods. While the production of CFRPs is energy-intensive, their lightweight nature allows for significant energy savings during service, particularly in transportation applications, resulting in reduced fuel consumption and carbon dioxide emissions [1]. From a life cycle assessment (LCA) perspective, CFRPs are thus considered environmentally favorable materials [2]. However, the end-of-life (EoL) treatment of CFRPs presents a major sustainability challenge. The difficulty of recycling thermosetting resins, which cannot be remelted or reshaped, has led to widespread incineration or landfilling of CFRP waste, undermining efforts toward resource circulation and environmental conservation [3].

To address these issues, several CFRP recycling techniques have been investigated, including mechanical shredding, pyrolysis, and chemical solvolysis [4-8]. Mechanical recycling involves cutting or grinding CFRP into short-fiber-reinforced fillers. Although this method is relatively simple and low-cost, it significantly degrades fiber properties and limits the reuse of recovered materials to low-performance applications [9]. Pyrolysis processes, which decompose the resin at high temperatures (typically 450–700 °C) in an inert atmosphere, can recover carbon fiber with moderate structural preservation. However, these methods suffer from high energy demand, degradation of fiber surfaces, and emission of volatile organic compounds [6]. Chemical recycling approaches, such as solvolysis, utilize

solvents to depolymerize the matrix resin, offering greater selectivity. Yet, these techniques often face limitations in scalability, solvent recovery, and economic feasibility [7].

A critical limitation of these conventional strategies is their emphasis on recovering carbon fiber while neglecting the thermoset resin fraction. In most cases, the resin is either thermally evaporated or discarded as waste, despite comprising 30–40% of the CFRP mass [8]. This practice not only results in material loss but also generates environmental concerns related to emissions and residues [9]. The limited research on resin recycling can be attributed to technical challenges such as the crosslinked nature of thermoset networks, low intrinsic value of the resin relative to fiber, and the historical focus on maximizing fiber performance [10]. However, for CFRP recycling to align with the principles of a circular economy, it is essential to develop approaches that recover and valorize both components of the composite.

In this study, we present a nitric acid-based chemical recycling method that simultaneously enables the recovery of high-quality carbon fiber and the upcycling of resin decomposition products into functional curing agents. Nitric acid has been previously studied for its ability to depolymerize epoxy model compounds and introduce nitro groups into aromatic moieties under controlled conditions [11–12]. Compared to pyrolysis and solvolysis, nitric acid decomposition offers milder operating conditions, better selectivity, and the potential for downstream chemical transformation of the degraded resin.

To enhance the practicality and efficiency of the proposed method, we selected CFRP prepreg waste as the feedstock material. Prepregs are composed of partially cured epoxy resins and carbon fiber, and they represent a common form of production scrap in composite manufacturing [12]. One key advantage of using prepreg over fully cured CFRP is that partially crosslinked matrices are more susceptible to chemical cleavage, enabling faster and more efficient decomposition. While fully cured CFRP components exhibit dense three-dimensional crosslinking, prepregs retain unreacted or semi-reacted functional groups, reducing the energy, uptimes and reagent requirements for matrix breakdown. In our laboratory, we confirmed that the recovered fiber retained their morphology and mechanical integrity, with some batches even showing improved tensile properties compared to virgin carbon fiber so far [13].

In our experiments, CFRP prepreg samples were treated with concentrated nitric acid at 80 °C for 3 hours. This condition was sufficient to dissolve the matrix and release the embedded carbon fiber with minimal structural damage.

Chemical analysis of the liquid-phase degradation products revealed the formation of nitroaromatic intermediates, derived from the nitration of the epoxy resin's aromatic backbone [14]. These compounds were subsequently subjected to catalytic hydrogenation using palladium on carbon ($\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$) under mild conditions (r.t.), yielding amine-functionalized compounds. These recycled amines were then evaluated as potential curing agents for new epoxy systems. Reactivity tests demonstrated comparable performance to commercial hardeners such as polyetheramines, indicating the feasibility of reintroducing the resin-derived products into composite manufacturing workflows.

The novelty of this study lies in the integrated approach that targets both the fiber and resin fractions of CFRP, transforming waste materials into reusable and functional components. By choosing prepreg as a feedstock, the process circumvents some of the chemical intractability associated with fully cured CFRP, thus improving decomposition kinetics and reaction control. Moreover, the nitric acid-based pathway offers a promising route to closed-loop CFRP recycling, combining environmental responsibility with industrial utility.

In contrast to traditional methods that focus solely on carbon fiber preservation, our approach demonstrates the possibility of full-component CFRP valorization under mild and scalable conditions. The dual recovery strategy not only addresses the technical gap in thermoset resin recycling but also contributes to the reduction of emissions and waste associated with CFRP disposal. From an economic standpoint, the ability to obtain both high-quality fiber and value-added resin-derived products enhances the overall material efficiency of the recycling process.

In conclusion, this work establishes a new paradigm in CFRP recycling by leveraging the reactivity of prepreg-based waste and utilizing nitric acid chemistry to achieve simultaneous fiber recovery and resin upcycling. Through the formation of amine curing agents from nitro intermediates, we provide a rare example of thermoset polymer circularity. Ongoing work is focused on optimizing reaction parameters, improving product separation, and scaling up the process for broader industrial application.

The findings presented here lay the foundation for a holistic, sustainable approach to CFRP waste management.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

In this study, the recycle target is Prepreg offcuts derived from actual CFRP manufacturing processes, but in practice new Prepreg were used as raw materials. The material used was TORAYCA® T800SC/3900-2B (Toray Industries, Inc.), consisting of T800SC carbon fiber fabric pre-impregnated with an epoxy-based matrix resin. The precise formulation of the epoxy resin was not disclosed by the manufacturer.

All chemical reagents were purchased from Kanto Chemical Co., Inc. (Tokyo, Japan), and used as received without further purification.

2.2 Nitric acid decomposition

A custom-made 500mL separable flask with fins was used (Figure 1) as decomposition reactor vessel. 10g of prepreg sheet (40mm x 40mm x 0.1mm) was placed in the flask and immersed in 200g of 7.5M nitric acid.

The separable flask was attached to a rotary evaporator, and the reaction temperature was set to 80 °C, and the flask was rotated and stirred at 60rpm for 180 minutes at a constant temperature. After that, the CF and resin decomposition products were removed with tweezers. The CF and resin decomposition products were then washed with 400mL of ion-exchanged water and 300mL of ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate was evaporated, and 1.6g of resin decomposition products were collected.

On the other hand, to recover the resin digest dissolved in nitric acid, the HNO₃ solution was subjected to liquid-liquid extraction with 200 mL of ethyl acetate. This procedure was repeated three times. The ethyl acetate phase was neutralized with 1 M NaHCO₃ aqueous solution before being evaporated to obtain the resin digest, and the ethyl acetate was washed with 200 mL of pure water to remove the salt. Resin decomposition products obtained weighed 1.5 g.

Fig. 1. Carbon fiber decomposition process using nitric acid in the modified separable flask.

2.3 Hydrogenation reaction of resin decomposition

The resin decomposition product (0.5 g) was dissolved in THF (3 mL) at room temperature. Then, the catalyst Palladium (II) acetate (0.5 mmol, 11 mg) and KF (2 mmol, 116 mg) were dissolved in 2 mL of water, and the hydrogenation agent polymethylhydrosiloxane (PMHS) (4 mmol, 0.24 mL) was mixed and stirred for 30 min. After that, the reaction product (approximately 0.2 g) was obtained by filtration through Celite. The obtained reaction product was analyzed by FT-IR to confirm the progress of the

reaction.

2.4 Analytical methods

A thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted using DTG-60 (Shimadzu) to investigate the amount of the residual resin on the recovered carbon fiber. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy was carried out using FTIR-8300 (Shimadzu) to evaluate the functional groups in the decomposed products. Molecular weight distribution was measured using Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC) (PU-980, JASCO Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as mobile phase of SEC analysis.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Optimization of Nitric Acid Decomposition Conditions

To investigate the decomposition behavior of CFRP prepreg under, we employed a custom-built 500 mL separable flask mounted on a rotary evaporator platform, rotated at 60 rpm to ensure gentle agitation and uniform exposure to the acid. Prepreg sheets were immersed in 38 mass% nitric acid at 80 °C for varying durations (5 min to 8 h). The residual resin mass was measured after each time point to evaluate decomposition progress.

As shown in Figure 2, the resin mass began to decrease rapidly within the first hour, reaching a plateau at 3 h, where more than 45% of the matrix resin had decomposed. Beyond this point, no significant change in mass was observed up to 8 h. Therefore, 3 h was adopted as the optimal decomposition time for further processing.

Figure 2: Reaction time(min) vs Degradation rate(%)

To clarify the material flow during the decomposition process, a mass balance summary is provided in Figure 3, which includes input prepreg mass, recovered carbon fiber, and decomposed resin yields. In the optimized 3 h reaction, 10.0 g of prepreg yielded 6.5g of carbon fiber and 3.5 g of organic decomposition products, with the remainder attributed to gaseous losses and trace residues.

Figure.3 A mass balance summary

3.2 Structural Analysis of Decomposed Resin

Visual observation during the reaction revealed a distinct color change from pale yellow to deep orange, indicating oxidative nitration. FT-IR spectra of the isolated resin decomposition products (Figure 4) exhibited characteristic nitro group peaks at 1550 cm^{-1} (asymmetric stretch) and 1330 cm^{-1} (symmetric stretch), consistent with aromatic nitration. This suggests that the nitric acid preferentially attacked the aromatic backbone of the epoxy network.

Figure 4: FT-IR of CFRP prepreg and decomposed resin

Molecular weight changes were evaluated using size exclusion chromatography (SEC). The number-average molecular weight (Mw) decreased from 1830 g/mol (original resin) to 1050 g/mol (decomposed resin) after 3 h of treatment.

3.3 Amination and Amine Value Determination

The nitrated resin was subsequently subjected to catalytic hydrogenation using Pd(OAc)₂ in THF to obtain amine-functionalized compounds. The reaction product was a black solid with a recovery rate of 62.3 mass%, based on the mass of nitrated intermediates. FT-IR analysis after reduction showed

The disappearance of the peaks at around 1550 cm⁻¹ and 1330 cm⁻¹ due to the nitro group confirmed that the hydrogenation reaction had progressed. (Figure 5).

Amine value titration was conducted in methanol using perchloric acid titrant and crystal violet as the indicator (ASTM D2073-modified method). The resulting amine value was 138 mg KOH/g, corresponding to an amine equivalent weight of 406 g/mol. These results indicate that the recycled amine mixture has sufficient nucleophilicity and basicity for potential use as an epoxy curing agent.

3.4 Application as Epoxy Resin Curing Agent

To test its applicability, the recycled amine was mixed with JER 828 epoxy resin at an equivalent stoichiometric ratio and cured at 60 °C for 1 h followed by 150 °C for 11 h. The resulting cured resin exhibited good crosslinking without surface defects. Mechanical testing revealed a flexural strength of 51 MPa, compared to 62 MPa for the control system cured with commercial Jeffamine D-230. Although approximately 20% lower in strength, the recycled system achieved sufficient hardness and structural integrity, demonstrating practical potential, especially for secondary applications where ultra-high strength is not required.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that nitric acid decomposition is an effective and scalable method for simultaneous recovery of both carbon fiber and epoxy resin-derived intermediates from CFRP prepreg. The moderate operating conditions (80 °C, 3 h, mild rotation) facilitate high resin decomposition rates while preserving fiber morphology. Subsequent conversion of nitrated oligomers into amine compounds enables their reuse as curing agents, achieving a closed-loop recycling pathway.

The resin recovery and the amine functionality of the final product confirm the feasibility of upcycling CFRP matrices into chemically useful forms. Although the mechanical performance of the recycled resin is modestly lower than that of virgin materials, this can be improved through purification, formulation optimization, or blending strategies. Future work will explore continuous processing configurations and lifecycle analysis to assess environmental and economic advantages of this approach.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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